

Academic Examination of the Concept of "Hierarchy" in Public Law

To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 5-9, 2023, p. 163 – 183. - 0099-0001-2309-0107.

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ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

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Abstract

The field of international law, like to other scholarly fields, relies on a body of established facts,

intuitive understandings, and historical narratives. The amalgamation of these fundamental elements contributes to the formation of the unique episteme of the field, which is distinguished by the paradigmatic structure of knowledge and speech, as per Foucault's definition of the notion. The observable epistemic reality pertains to the fundamentally anarchic character inherent in the international law system. The primary cause for the disorderly and unorganized state of affairs may be attributed to the lack of a centralized and hierarchically organized governing body tasked with the creation and implementation of laws. In some

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instances, national legal systems possess the ability to use intricate and sophisticated institutional structures that enable them to adopt laws and wield legal coercion. In contrast, international law is seen as a form of governance that exhibits a more horizontally organized framework compared to domestic law. This phenomenon may be attributed to the decentralization of power and enforcement pertaining to crucial legal obligations, including legislation, legal interpretation, and law enforcement. The notion of horizontality, also known as the absence of hierarchy, is universally acknowledged by the majority as a significant component in comprehending global matters and serves as a fundamental foundation for initiating discussions on matters pertaining to international law.

The significance of this discovery is notably apparent within the realm of welding theory. Conventional narratives on the establishment of international law depict a heterogeneous and inconsistent structure whereby states, as equivalent sovereign entities, adopt norms for their own governance using a range of approaches and protocols. These techniques and procedures possess the capacity to be used concurrently or in contrast to one another, and no one procedure exhibits superiority over the other in terms of normativity.

Keywords: Public Law, Public Administration, Hierarchy, Hierarchy in Public Law, Non-Hierarchy

Introduction

The sources of international law are often regarded as having equivalent rank and significance. This implies that a norm originating from one source has no inherent superiority over a norm originating from another source. This implies that there exists no constitution with more authority than ordinary legislation, no statutory laws that surpass common law, and no obligatory higher court rulings for lower court judgments. According to this perspective, the formation of the international legal system has rendered the concept of a formal hierarchy of resources incompatible with its structure. Nevertheless, it is crucial to acknowledge that within the realm of international legal thinking and practice, there are several hierarchies notwithstanding the functional equivalence of resources. The presence of these hierarchies, although not overtly acknowledged, is pervasive inside the system and influences the comprehension, development, and implementation of international law.

The present study seeks to investigate two distinct categorizations of resource hierarchies. The first classification is widely recognized as "informal hierarchies of superiority". Informal

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hierarchies emerge as a result of acknowledging the functional or formal equivalence of resources. However, particular actors, such as governments, courts, and academics, tend to demonstrate biases towards certain resources. This desire is rooted on the belief that these resources possess distinct attributes or uphold certain ideals that are seen advantageous, such as precision, adaptability, and comprehensiveness. The aforementioned preferences pertain to adaptable and transitory hierarchies that are influenced by a range of elements, including settings, events, the identities of legal individuals, and the aims they want to accomplish, as will be elucidated shortly. Hierarchies emerge due to the inclusion of a normative standpoint, whereby some resources are evaluated as superior (in terms of their goodness, effectiveness, and adherence to democratic principles), while others are seen as inferior (in terms of their weakness, inefficiency, and lack of legitimacy).

The prioritization of individual resources' normative worth is not a characteristic of the second kind of resource hierarchy. Conversely, the emphasis is on the pragmatic aspects of resources, namely their practical functionality. The presence of these hierarchies might be ascribed to the inherent biases within the systems that are responsible for the establishment of international law. While these processes have a tendency to favor some actors, voices, and experiences, such as governments, powerful nations, individuals of white ethnicity, and transnational capital, they also tend to marginalize other entities, such as non-state organizations, less influential nations, individuals of non-white ethnicity, and workers. Despite the prevalent dedication to legislative parity, the global system incorporates and often institutionalizes disparities throughout the development of international law. While substantive hierarchies are not unique to international law, they are prevalent within the international system.

The lack of fixed, pre-determined hierarchies among the recognized sources of international law does not imply that the international system works on a just and equitable basis. The evolution of international law is marked by prominent power structures shown in the form of hierarchical systems. The aforementioned hierarchies are not associated with recognized embodiments of international law. Instead, they pertain to hierarchies within the sources of international law and their functional dynamics in everyday implementation. The subsequent kind

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of hierarchy must be denoted as "substantive legislative hierarchies." Given the distinctive attributes of the subject matter, a methodology that incorporates both schematic and impressionistic elements will be used due to its inherent nature. The next study will investigate informal and material hierarchies, acknowledging that they represent just a subset of the hierarchical patterns discernible within the realm of philosophy and resource management. The emphasis will be placed on representative and noteworthy examples due to limitations in geographical capacity. This implies that more models, such as those based on social class and racial hierarchies, will undergo analysis across diverse contexts. Due to the aforementioned rationale, two further sets of inquiries were excluded from the introductory segment of this investigation. The primary concern is to the notion of the hierarchy of norms, which concerns the interplay between individual norms or collections of norms, depending on their substance, irrespective of the source of these norms (e.g., the elevated standing of jus cogens in comparison to the principle of lex posterior). The topic under consideration may be conceptually distinguished from the hierarchical structure of sources, and a thorough examination of this can be found in several academic publications. The second concern is to the relationship between conventional sources of international law and developing processes of law-making that surpass national boundaries, often known as "beyond the state." These mechanisms are enabled by transnational governance entities, both public and commercial in nature.

The paper presents a comprehensive examination of the notion of "trans-state" in the context of emerging modalities of legislative processes. The statement questions the legitimacy of the "no hierarchy" hypothesis, a key concept in the theory of resources. The primary contention made within this article is the fallacy of the "no hierarchy" idea. The law-making method within the global framework is characterized as being horizontal in nature, as it adheres to the notion of equal significance between resources and the capacity to enact legislation autonomously. Nevertheless, it is crucial to acknowledge that the allocation of resources is significantly impacted by various social stratifications often known as hierarchies. Hence, the assertion posited in the first statement is misleading. Based on the aforementioned facts, it is academically determined that this theory should be considered insufficient owing to its negative consequences in terms of both

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descriptive accuracy and normative concerns. The following part endeavors to provide significant elucidations of the fundamental principle of the "non-hierarchy" argument. The fundamental principle posits that sources of international law has equal legal standing as processes for creating law and are not hierarchically prioritized in terms of significance or dominance.

Methodology

Despite facing extensive criticism for its limits, insufficiency, and relevance, Article 38(1) of the Statute of the International Court of Justice remains a crucial point of reference in discussions surrounding the development of international law. The overwhelming consensus is that this signifies the communal comprehension about the categorization of sources of international law. The aforementioned sources have been succinctly presented in a certain sequence (from a to d), which may create the perception of a rudimentary hierarchy. The drafting of Article 38 included a suggestion to create a dedicated sequence for the examination of the sources referenced in the provision. The suggested ordering would provide more priority to conventions over tradition and conventions over basic principles.

In the realm of legal principles, primary sources, including treaties and customary practices, are often regarded as the only authentic sources. In contrast, supplementary sources such as court judgments and doctrinal works are seen as valuable tools for the interpretation and elucidation of fundamental legal sources. To provide more explanation, one might posit that the field of international law inside academia has a discernible episteme, as described by the philosopher Michel Foucault. The aforementioned episteme may be regarded as the discipline paradigmatic framework for cognition and reasoning. Similar to other fields within academia, the topic of international law is founded upon a framework consisting of known facts, intuitions, and historical narratives.

Literature Review

One crucial aspect to contemplate is the inherent anarchic character of the international law system from an epistemic standpoint. The absence of a centralized and hierarchically organized authority tasked with the creation and implementation of laws is the primary cause for the observed state of disorder and chaos. In several instances, national legal systems have the ability to use intricate and sophisticated institutional structures that possess the authority to promulgate laws and apply legal coercion. In contrast, international law is seen as a form of administration that exhibits a more horizontally organized framework when compared to domestic law. The aforementioned phenomenon may be attributed to the decentralization and centralization of judicial power, as well as the effective discharge of crucial legal duties, including legislation, adjudication, and enforcement. The notion of horizontality, denoting the absence of hierarchical arrangements, is often considered a significant component in comprehending global phenomena and serves as a fundamental foundation for examining international law. The significance of this discovery is notably apparent within the domain of welding theory. Conventional narratives on the establishment of international law depict a heterogeneous and non-uniform structure, whereby states, as equivalent sovereign entities, develop norms for their own governance using a range of methodologies and protocols. These techniques and procedures possess the capacity to be used concurrently or in contrast to one another, and neither procedure has superiority over the other in terms of normativity. In the realm of scientific discourse, it is widely acknowledged that sources of international law are regarded as possessing comparable rank and prestige. This implies that the significance of a norm derived from one source is fundamentally equivalent to that of a norm formulated from another source. This entails the lack of a constitution that has more authority than ordinary legislation, the absence of statutory laws that surpass common law, and the absence of legally binding supreme court rulings for lower court judgments. According to this perspective, the creation of the international legal system has resulted in the detachment of the concept of a predetermined, formal hierarchy of resources. Nevertheless, it is crucial to acknowledge that within the realm of international legal thinking and practice, many hierarchies exist notwithstanding the functional equivalence of resources. The presence of these hierarchies,

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although not overtly acknowledged, is pervasive inside the system and influences the formulation, development, and implementation of international law. The present study seeks to investigate two distinct categorizations of resource hierarchies.

The first classification may be characterized as "informal dominance hierarchies". Informal hierarchies emerge as a result of acknowledging the functional or formal equivalence of resources. However, some actors such as governments, judges, and academics hold the belief that these resources possess distinct attributes or desired values, such as stability, versatility, or universality. The aforementioned preferences are subject to change and are transient hierarchies that are influenced by several elements, including settings, situations, legal identities of individuals, and desired objectives, as will be seen in the following discussion. Hierarchies arise from the process of discriminating resources based on normative evaluations, whereby some resources are deemed superior (exemplary, effective, democratic) while others are judged inferior (insufficient, inadequate). The second category of resource hierarchy places emphasis not only on the inherent worth of individual resources, but also on their actual functionality, sometimes referred to as the pragmatics of resources. The presence of these hierarchies might be ascribed to the inherent biases within the systems that are responsible for the establishment of international law. These processes have a tendency to give priority to certain actors, voices, and experiences, including governments, dominant powers, individuals of white male identity, and transnational capital. Conversely, they tend to marginalize other entities, such as non-state organizations, less influential powers, individuals of brown female identity, and labor.

Despite the widespread dedication to achieving legislative equality, it is evident that the global system perpetuates and sometimes even formalizes inequities throughout the development of international law. Although substantive hierarchies are not exclusive to international law, they are often seen within the international system. The lack of fixed, pre-determined hierarchies among the recognized sources of international law does not imply that the international system works on a just and equitable basis. The creation of international law is marked by robust power structures that are manifested as hierarchical organizations. The aforementioned hierarchies are not associated with recognized expressions of international law. Instead, they pertain to hierarchies within the sources of international law and their functional dynamics in everyday implementation.

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The subsequent kind of hierarchy will be referred to as "substantive legislative hierarchies." The next study will use a methodology that combines a schematic and impressionistic approach, taking into consideration the distinctive characteristics of the subject matter. The hierarchies examined within this discourse do not represent the only hierarchical patterns discernible in the theory and implementation of resources. Given the limitations imposed by geographical limits, the emphasis will be placed on situations that are typical and noteworthy. Consequently, other patterns, such as social class and racial hierarchies, will be examined via diverse analytical frameworks.

Findings

The primary problem is to the notion of the hierarchy of norms, which examines the interplay between individual norms or collections of norms, depending on their substance, irrespective of the source of these norms (e.g., the elevated position of jus cogens in comparison to savings law). The topic under consideration may be conceptually distinguished from the hierarchical structure of sources, and an exhaustive examination of this matter can be found in several academic publications. The second concern is to the correlation between conventional sources of international law and developing mechanisms of law formation that transcend the territorial boundaries of particular nations. The contemporary methods of legislation include a combination of public and private transnational governing entities. Nevertheless, it is crucial to acknowledge that the regulation of sources is marked by several distinctions or hierarchies of status, so rendering the aforementioned assertion false. Consequently, the theory in question was deemed unsuitable for acceptance due to the inherent issues it presents in both its descriptive and normative aspects. The primary emphasis is on informal hierarchies of superiority, with the objective of offering significant elucidations for the fundamental tenet of the "no hierarchy" contention. The primary concept examined in this discourse is to the notion that sources of international law possess an equal standing as instruments for establishing legal standards, devoid of any predetermined hierarchy of significance or supremacy.

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Argument

The dominant viewpoint posits that it functions as a mechanism for articulating the widely acknowledged comprehension of the categorization of international law sources. The difference between main and secondary sources of international law is well acknowledged among experts. Primary sources, such as treaties and ancient practices, are often regarded as the only authentic origins of legal principles. In contrast, auxiliary sources, such as court judgments and academic literature, are regarded only as instruments for the interpretation and elucidation of fundamental sources of law. Hence, it may be inferred that this assertion posits a difference between the use of physical coercion and the practice of convincing by rational argumentation. The provided definition of authority aligns entirely with the concept of "binding" or "mandatory" authority within the legal system. Legal professionals, such as attorneys and judges, are obligated to adhere to the statutory mandate, irrespective of their personal agreement or disagreement with its substance. Nevertheless, within the realm of Law, the term "authority" extends beyond the confines of obligatory information that necessitates adherence. Instead, it often pertains to non-binding information. The word "non-binding jurisdiction" has a pejorative undertone in its denotation, since it pertains to any legal provisions that lack obligatory force, so indicating that law drafters are not compelled to adhere to them. Therefore, the term's definition might be seen as being contrary to conventional notions of authority. The rationale for this phenomenon might perhaps be attributed to the conventional interpretation.

In relation to non-binding or persuasive authority, the author asserts that legal authors often use it when they find its substantive material convincing. They acknowledge that the concept of authority without an associated obligation of obedience may seem contradictory, but note that this issue has received less exploration. In this regard, it does not possess the characteristics often associated with authority in the classical context. Nevertheless, the conventional perspective is in direct opposition to prevailing customs and has been effectively disproven by Frederick Schauer. Persuasive authority is often referenced for reasons unrelated to its actual substance, namely for its authoritative nature. Consequently, persuasive authority has a significance that extends beyond its intrinsic material worth. referred to as the persuasive authority weight. Numerous academics have conducted research on this weight, leading to its widespread recognition and acceptance in

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academic discourse. On the contrary, the prevailing and enduring conventional belief posits that persuasive authority is primarily selected based on its ability to effectively convey crucial information, and that the act of being identified as such does not significantly trouble a majority of individuals. The capacity to disregard some elements is widely acknowledged as an integral aspect of the prevailing legal framework. In contemporary legal analysis, the word "authority" has acquired a broader connotation, including several forms of referenced material. This aspect has significance due to the broadening scope of authority, including many forms of information. In the realm of legal analysis, the inclusion of such diverse sources has become a routine practice. The materials used in this manner are situated outside the clearly delineated realm of legal sources that attorneys traditionally depended upon.

The issue has been further intensified by recent significant shifts in information accessibility. The establishment of this legislative practice has resulted in the emergence of several fields of study that examine the appropriate significance and role of external sources in the interpretation of enacted legislation. Illustrative instances of these specific subdivisions of analysis include administrative agency remarks, legislative history, construction rules, and dictionaries. This analysis examines the significance and relevance of external sources in comprehending the legal framework that is enacted. Consequently, the persuasive authority category lacks differentiation, leading to a transition away from interpretive tools like legislative history and rules of construction. Instead, it encompasses sources that have no direct connection to the area of law, such as empirical studies from other disciplines. Nevertheless, the widely used concept of the "hierarchy of authority" continues to serve as the primary framework for establishing a legal authority structure, systematically disregarding any authorities that lack binding power. The conventional authority model offers a uniform hierarchy of levels inside an organization. There are only two specific types of resources that use a restricted categorization based on binary distinctions: binding/non-binding and primary/secondary. This paradigm is predicated upon the notion that main sources possess the highest degree of reliability, while secondary sources exhibit the lowest degree of reliability.

The exercise of power is a subject of considerable complexity and intrigue, beyond the seeming simplicity of these aforementioned distinctions. Among the many factors contributing to this complexity, the unpredictability inherent in the realm of law stands out as particularly significant. The hierarchical structure of power, often seen as the prevailing metaphor for authority, does not align effectively with the inherent essence of authority. The portrayal of authority as an absolute and unchanging entity in this context is flawed and does not accurately reflect the true nature of authority. The conventional perspective has long maintained a steadfast portrayal of the Law as a finite compilation of immutable sources. Nevertheless, the lack of elucidation about the rationale for the use of non-binding sources by legal decision makers is apparent. In contemporary times, there has been a notable surge in the diversity and volume of materials used in the realm of legal analysis. In the current era characterized by the abundance of information, it is difficult to conceive of a measure that would effectively limit the use of readily available resources. There is currently no evidence to suggest that the upward trend in the availability of permissible legal resources will experience a reversal in the immediate future. Furthermore, there is currently no indication that the upward trend in the availability of permissible legal resources will undergo a reversal in the foreseeable future. In contemporary culture, there is an increasing divergence between the conventional notion of legal authority and the practical use of power. It is important to provide a more thorough viewpoint and comprehension of the sources used in legal analysis and their inherent attributes. The examination of power within the legal profession, judiciary, law student body, and academic discourse is of utmost importance. This phenomenon has an impact on the comprehension of legal analysis within the legal profession. There is a pressing need to enhance the lexicon, use more sophisticated metaphors, and utilize descriptive instruments when referencing the sources employed in legal discourse. This is crucial in order to effectively tackle the fundamental underlying matters pertaining to the judicial assessment of what constitutes law and the rationale behind such determinations. This will enable us to address fundamental inquiries.

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"Binding" and "Non-binding"

The two prevalent classifications, namely "binding" and "non-binding," as well as "primary" and "secondary," are characterized by their inherent simplicity. To start, it is important to note that non-binding authority are often used for their status, rather than only relying on the information they provide, contrary to common belief. Consequently, the extent of authority cannot be confined to a binary classification of either absolute or negligible; instead, it is more appropriately characterized as a spectrum. Furthermore, the conventional perspective on authority, which perceives it as a fixed hierarchy, fails to adequately capture the continuous evolution in the significance and provenance of accepted sources. The conventional conception of authority is rooted on a hierarchical framework. Hence, the hierarchy of authority has deficiencies in terms of both accuracy and comprehensiveness.

The concept of authority is seen in this context as a pluralistic endeavor rather than a hierarchical structure, with the aim of constructing a more intricate and all-encompassing understanding of legal authority. In the setting of contentious legal issues, the present dual strategy proves to be of little use. In the context of challenging legal inquiries, the available resources for decision makers, except from those that are legally binding, are not elucidated. The act of oversimplifying authority hinders the ability to engage in meaningful investigation and get a deeper comprehension of the exercise of legal power. The existing approach fails to include the element of choice and operates on the assumption that legal outcomes are predicted by legal norms outlined within a fixed collection of legal sources. This assumption poses a challenge since it engenders a fallacious inference about the factors that govern legal repercussions. The acknowledgement of the authoritative influence of persuasive authority provides an opportunity to explore the potential theoretical underpinnings of the use of non-binding authority, a common practice in legal analysis, but one that is entirely at the discretion of the user. A comprehensive understanding of the underlying logic behind the practice of quoting non-binding sources in legal decision-making helps enhance the explanation and predictability of this phenomenon.

Educators responsible for instructing law students would significantly benefit from cultivating a more intricate and comprehensive understanding of power dynamics. Law students are especially prone to being deceived by the conventional model of power. Nonetheless, it is of equal significance for those engaged in professional practice and judicial decision-making, as well as others who may derive knowledge from them, to possess a shared conceptual framework and vocabulary that enables them to articulate their intricate exercise of power. Within the cohort of individuals that possess the capacity to acquire knowledge from these sources, there exists a subgroup that stands to gain advantageous outcomes as a result. Ultimately, the introduction of an alternative viewpoint on authority serves as an impetus for scholars to go further into the intricate realm of legal analysis.

What Does It Mean for the Legal Profession to Have Fundamentally Unlimited Powers?

Is the inclusion of the idea of authority still seen significant in the realm of legal analysis? The existing authority hierarchy is said to mirror the legal authority landscape, although it is significantly deficient in its current form. The use of shortcuts as a means to address complex legal inquiries impedes the development of a comprehensive theoretical comprehension of the essence and limits of law. The hierarchical structure of power is a barrier to the development of a comprehensive theoretical comprehension of the nature of law. Throughout history, the establishment of legal power has been founded upon two widely acknowledged concepts.

“Legal authority may be categorized into two main types: obligatory, which is binding, and persuasive, which is non-binding. Additionally, legal authority can also be classified as either primary or secondary.”

When engaging in discussions on the significance of authority, the classification of essential and compelling elements tends to get considerable focus. The primary/secondary distinction delineates legal concepts from non-legal ideas, serving just this function. Both

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categories contribute to the perpetuation of the notion of a very simplified authority system, whereby legal authors are just tasked with identifying applicable laws based on a preconceived set of norms (which are never critically examined).

The Weight of Legal Authority According to the Traditional Understanding

The fundamental concept guiding legal authority is that writers must largely depend on peremptory authority, which is sometimes referred to as "binding," "governing," or "controlling," while constructing legal analyses. An authority that is exclusively constituted by primary sources, which are described as original documents or firsthand accounts of events, individuals, or phenomena. The only authority that may be considered significant is perquisite authority. This represents the established approach. The inclusion of requisite sources is widely accepted and often presented without elaboration. The defining characteristic of authority categorized as necessary is its inherent need for obedience, irrespective of its substance. The interrelationship of constitutional law, legislative actions, and jurisprudence is little explored within this particular setting. Constitutions have the highest level of power, followed by legislation and then judicial rulings. The hierarchy of authority primarily focuses on the relative significance of court judgments, with less attention given to the allocation of power across other institutions. The fundamental purpose of the hierarchy of authority is to ascertain the appropriate sources that need to be consulted in a specific scenario. The objective is to identify or ascertain.

Compulsory authority can only be determined if a particular jurisdiction and its corresponding decision-making body have been duly created. The concept of the "hierarchy of authority" that governs the use of coercive force is well recognized and largely undisputed. However, when a specific jurisdiction has been established, the obligatory framework of jurisdiction that is relevant to a given issue may often be ascertained with relative ease. The use of obligatory power is governed by the "hierarchy of authority." The vertical precedent is a fundamental principle in the legal system, wherein lower courts are obligated to adhere to the rulings made by higher courts within the hierarchical structure of the court system. Vertical

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precedent is often seen as a rigid principle that does not allow for any deviations. It is widely acknowledged as the most influential and authoritative kind of precedent.

Horizontal precedent is considered to be one of the less complex forms of legal precedent. Courts may be legally obligated to adhere to rulings rendered other courts of equivalent jurisdiction. Nevertheless, it is important to note that a court is only obligated to adhere to the decision made in the vertical judgment, while the other portions of the opinion have no legal significance. The legal significance of a horizontal precedent is contingent upon the jurisdiction in question. In certain instances, horizontal precedent lacks significant binding force within the jurisdiction of many minor claim courts. Within the realm of the judicial system, the phenomenon of horizontal view decision-making is seen to be very scarce in district courts, while conversely, it is predominantly regarded as an unequivocal principle in appellate courts. According to the court's doctrine, federal appellate courts are horizontally bound by the decisions of preceding courts. The court renders panel judgments, unless they are constrained by precedent set by prior panel decisions.

Secondary authority is sometimes used as a resource for the purpose of identifying, condensing, or comprehending significant rules. It is noteworthy to mention that the lists typically consist of primary sources, which are conventional legal documents sometimes referred to as "materials with the most typical legal appearance". The phrases "secondary" and "persuasive" imply that these sources should be categorized only as "other" sources, since they lack primary authority and are not legally binding. The entrance model of authority is characterized by a hierarchical structure of established primary sources that have remained unaltered for the previous two centuries. The statement offered posits a concept of authority that aligns with the mechanical viewpoint prevalent in the domain of law. This approach posits that the resolution of legal issues is contingent upon the application of established rules. Accordingly, legal authors are obligated to identify just the essential legal sources in order to reach the suitable conclusion. The viewpoint often known as the rule-based worldview is a defining characteristic of the legal realm. The disregard for non-binding resources over time results in a progressive decrease in the significance attributed to these resources.

Authority Hierarchy

As previously elucidated, the conventional understanding of authority has two fundamental characteristics: duality, wherein sources are categorized as either binding or non-binding, and a static attribute, whereby there is no indication of prospective changes in legal sources or their significance through time. The hierarchical model has notable deficiencies in all aspects and seems to be incongruent with actual situations. The idea of continuity refers to the concentration of all power. The term "weight of authority" is often used to convey the notion of authority. The use of the term "weight" in a metaphorical sense enables the delineation of several distinctions. The apparent dichotomy between the two is sometimes depicted as insurmountable; authority is either obligatory or discretionary. The primary concern within the hierarchy of authority is to the delineation of binding power among different sources of authority. Nevertheless, the conventional interpretation of authority lacks the ability to adequately elucidate or delve into the concept of significance, except from the distinction between obligatory (carrying the highest level of significance) and non-obligatory (lacking significance) decisions. The demarcation between these two groups is often depicted as impassable. This approach posits that the significance of persuasive authority lies not in its intrinsic value, but rather in its ability to have a substantial persuasive impact. In the absence of substantial significance, there seems to be little justification for the continued organization of persuasive authority, since its primary characteristic lies in its non-binding nature. Numerous academics, including Schauer, have acknowledged that persuasive authority is invoked not just due to the persuasive strength of its content, but also for reasons unrelated to its content. These reasons are rooted in authoritative considerations that align with the classical conception of authority. It is improper to cite a source only based on its persuasive ability.

The Widespread View of Persuasive Authority

In practical application, persuasive authority is often used in a manner akin to imperative authority, as elucidated by Schauer.

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" While courts often reference legal sources due to actual and substantive persuasion, it seems that the majority of judicial use of supposed persuasive authority stems from the reliance on authority rather than the power of persuasion."

When a court is confronted with the task of applying a doctrine for the first time, it may choose to reference many precedents in order to establish the validity and applicability of that doctrine. The credibility of a theory is positively correlated with the amount of agreement across different constituencies, since the cumulative impact of consensus tends to hold substantial authority. Schauer proposes the use of the phrase "discretionary authority" as a more precise descriptor for the power that a legal writer exercises at their own discretion, as opposed to the term "persuasive authority."

The concept of "persuasive authority" may seem paradoxical, given that sources referenced for their persuasive influence are not often regarded as authoritative, irrespective of their substance. The word "voluntary" does not necessarily connote that the elected authority was selected only based on its capacity to persuade. This assertion poses a challenge to the conventional notion that discretionary authority is primarily selected based on its capacity to influence others via persuasive means. In accordance with the aforementioned requirements, it would be appropriate to persist in use Schauer's nomenclature for the duration of this article. The idea indicated above presents a contradiction to the counsel given on the use of discretion, notwithstanding the prevailing portrayal that discretion is employed only for its fundamental substance. In contrast to commonly held beliefs, the prominence of characteristics connected to social status provides support for the notion that discretion is often used in an authoritarian manner. The aforementioned perspective is substantiated by actual data. If we just analyze the information offered by these discretionary entitlements, there would be no need to assess the relative importance of the different forms of discretionary entitlements. Every governing body will undergo an independent evaluation based only on the quality of the topics presented, disregarding any variables linked to their position or standing. Discussions pertaining to the accurate use of a source within authoritative settings always center around the proper citation of such source. This assertion is true irrespective of the specific sort of authority being discussed. Within the discourse

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surrounding unpublished opinions and the question of the "quotability" of foreign law, it is commonly acknowledged that none of these sources has legally binding power. The primary emphasis is on determining the suitability of using these sources as supplementary citations. One may posit that the omission of reference for foreign legislation utilized only for substantive reasons could possibly mitigate conflicts. Likewise, the controversy regarding inexplicable viewpoints does not center on their obligatory character, but instead on varying degrees of authoritativeness.

The inclusion of a questionable reference serves the objective of properly crediting the concept to its original source, so mitigating the risk of plagiarism in the lack of a definitive explanation. Quotations often have a dual function, since they are used not only to provide proper attribution but also to provide credibility and authority to the discourse. The aforementioned declarations recognize the persuasive impact of non-binding sources, considering both their authority and substance. Nevertheless, they are unwilling to acknowledge any distinction or discordance between these two rationales. Although the rationale for favoring discretion is generally acknowledged, there is frequently a failure to recognize the discrepancy between these justifications and the prevalent notion that persuasive authority is selected based on its substance. The established boundaries of essential power may be analogized to the physical and administrative boundaries of a nation-state. The boundary line that delineates the territorial division between the two states is conspicuously well-defined and evident when seen in a cartographic depiction. Nevertheless, the line's visibility is often impeded when seen from a lower vantage point. The distinction between binding and non-binding authority is a well-established notion within the legal field, including legal professionals and scholars alike. Nevertheless, when it comes to the precise construction of legal arguments, discerning the difference is not as straightforward. The line between these two concepts gets more blurred when discretionary power is used in a manner that carries weight and, in several instances, obligatory authority is seen as ineffective. Legal decision makers do not only depend on authoritative sources for assistance and do not selectively augment them based on significant persuasion; This picture is too simplified. Due to its substantial effect that is not contingent on the particular setting, discretionary power exhibits similarities to obligatory authority that beyond the boundaries of a hierarchical structure. This phenomenon may be attributed to the prioritization of choice above required authority.

Conclusion

It is observed that decision makers inside the legal system often use non-binding sources in a manner akin to examining authoritative sources. The acceptance of secondary sources, such as jury instructions or restatements, as credible evidence of the law is not exclusively contingent upon their ability to convince based on the strength of their arguments. The examination of the suitability of exercising discretion for approved reasons is beyond the purview of this article. On the other hand, discretion is sometimes used as a means to manifest an authoritarian characteristic, therefore attributing it a comparable degree of significance as coercive authority. In summary, the notion of weight of authority is not a binary distinction but rather a complex and flexible idea. There are notable variations in the degree of discretionary judicial viewpoints. The presence of variety is particularly apparent within the realm of jurisprudence. Over the course of time, a multitude of behaviors have surfaced that acknowledge the significance ascribed to diverse viewpoints in different contexts. Nevertheless, it is important to acknowledge that the concept of "weight" remains incompletely defined within the scope of this particular situation. This reasoning is applicable to both binding precedents and persuasive precedents. While it is evident that tiny weight adjustments are often tolerated, the existing structure of authority lacks the ability to differentiate between the many nuanced weight changes that frequently arise in real-world situations. Consequently, the model fails to adequately capture the intricacies inherent in real-world scenarios. The consistency of the vertical priority effect's uniformity may vary across different circumstances. While several instances possess legal validity, the degrees of jurisdiction might exhibit substantial variations. The word "superior precedent" has particular significance since it is often used to describe instances that have been firmly embedded in legal theory and culture, and are considered to be exempt from reconsideration or nullification.

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RESTRICTION

In this study, which is built around a better understanding of the relationship between the phenomena of power and social control, the boundaries of these two concepts are determined and this evaluation is carried out with the information provided from the sources obtained by taking into account the scope of the research. This study is globally limited to the scientific studies on the subject.

NOTICES

Evaluation: Evaluated by internal and external experts.

Conflict of Interest: The author declares that there is no conflict of interest related to this study.

Financial Support: The author did not report any financial support for the study.

ETHICS DECLARATION

The publication ethics of this journal; It is a scientific journal in the field of social sciences that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in accordance with the main criteria specified as openness, honesty, respect for the findings and work of other publishers and objectivity.

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